

Co-ordination Catalysts in the Hydrogenation of Benzene*

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(a) Bisacetylacetonate-ethylenediiminonickel(II)-lithium aluminium hydride, (b) bis-salicylaldehyde-ethylene-diiminonickel(II)-lithium aluminium hydride and (c) cobalt(II) disalicylaldehyde-lithium aluminium hydride have been prepared and successfully used as catalysts for the hydrogenation of benzene to cyclohexane. The hydrogenation experiments carried out in a rotary autoclave indicated that 200° was a critical temperature for the reaction. A cold hydrogen pressure exceeding 60 atmosphere was not of any significant advantage. The optimum value for the atomic ratio of transition metal to aluminium was 1 : 4. The extent of hydrogenation depended on the concentration of chelate; there was practically no hydrogenation below 0.0005 mole per 40 ml of benzene. The hydrated chelate appeared to be much more active than the dehydrated one for the system (a).

At present there are a number of co-ordination catalysts¹⁻³ for the hydrogenation of alkenes, alkynes and aromatics. The catalysts available for the hydrogenation of benzene comprise noble metal and Ziegler-Natta type systems. The high cost and difficulty in the preparation and handling of these catalysts acted as incentives for the development of a new group of suitable catalysts consisting of acetylacetonates of cobalt, nickel and iron in combination with lithium aluminium hydride for the hydrogenation of benzene and other alkyl benzenes^{4,5}. Since then, (a) bisacetylacetonate-ethylenediiminonickel(II)-lithium aluminium hydride, (b) bis-salicylaldehyde-ethylenediiminonickel(II)-lithium aluminium hydride and (c) cobalt(II) disalicylaldehyde-lithium aluminium hydride have been prepared and found to be active catalysts.

Experimental

(1) Preparation of the Complexes

(a) Bisacetylacetonate-ethylenediiminonickel(II)⁶

One mole of anhydrous ethylenediamine was added to two moles of acetylacetonate when considerable heat was evolved. A straw coloured substance separating on cooling was crystallized twice from water and dried under reduced pressure. The yellowish-white crystals melted at 110°-112°.

An acetone solution of bisacetylacetonate-ethylenediimine was refluxed with nickel hydroxide for six hours. The unreacted metal hydroxide was filtered off and the metal chelate was precipitated from the filtrate by the addition of water. The brown-red precipitate of bisacetylacetonate-ethylenediiminonickel(II)-dihydrate was filtered under suction. When required, this was dried at 110° to give the dehydrated chelate. (Found: N 9.81, Ni 20.65; Anal. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₈O₂N₂Ni: N 9.97, Ni 20.89).

(b) Bis-salicylaldehyde-ethylenediiminonickel(II)⁷

Bis-salicylaldehyde-ethylenediimine was prepared by treating the alcoholic solutions of one mole of ethylenediamine with two moles of salicylaldehyde. The acetone solution of the ligand was refluxed with an excess of nickel hydroxide for six hours. The unreacted hydroxide was removed by filtration.

To the filtrate a limited amount of water was added to separate salicylaldehyde-ethylenediimine. After the free Schiff's base had been filtered off, an excess of water was added to the filtrate. The resultant precipitate was washed with alcohol to remove any remaining traces of free ligand. (Found: N 8.42, Ni: 18.15; Anal. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₄O₂N₂Ni: N 8.58, Ni 18.40).

(c) Cobalt(II) disalicylaldehyde⁸

Approximately half-saturated solutions of cobalt acetate in 50 per cent alcohol were treated with the stoichiometric amounts of salicylaldehyde. The reactants were thoroughly mixed and allowed to stand at room temperature until the reactions were complete. The precipitated products were filtered, washed successively with water, alcohol and ether, and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: C 52.91, H 3.65; Anal. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₀O₄Co. H₂O: C 52.83, H 3.77).

(2) Hydrogenation Procedure :

The experiments were carried out in a 500 ml rotary autoclave. No solvent was employed since the complexes were soluble in the substrate, benzene. On charging the substrate, reducing agent and the complex, the autoclave was repeatedly flushed with hydrogen and then the cold pressure

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was raised to the desired level. The autoclave was heated to the required temperature over a period of one hour. It was refilled with hydrogen from time to time to maintain the desired hot pressure. After the reaction was over, the autoclave was cooled and discharged. A black to greyish-black suspension was obtained in different cases. The precipitate was filtered. The filtrate was yellow in colour owing to the traces of soluble chelate. On distillation, a clear and colourless liquid was obtained.

(3) Analysis of the Product :

The benzene-cyclohexane system was analysed by the sulphuric acid-phosphorous pentoxide absorption method⁹. A few samples were also analysed by uv absorption spectrophotometry. The results obtained by the two methods tallied. However the u. v. method did not respond well to the analysis of the samples containing more than 90 per cent cyclohexane.

Results and Discussion

The experimental variables in the present study were temperature, transition metal to aluminium atomic ratio, catalyst concentration and the cold hydrogen pressure. The time of reaction was noted as the duration between the attainment of the required temperature and the constancy of the pressure.

(i) Effect of Temperature :

In the case of the catalyst systems (a) and (b), the reaction started at about 200° and became exorbitantly fast at 230°. With the catalyst system (c) the reaction started at 150° and the rate increased with the increase of temperature. A typical set of data is given in Table 1 while Fig. 1 illustrates the point.

TABLE 1—HYDROGENATION OF BENZENE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

[Catalyst : cobalt(II) disalicylaldehyde-lithium aluminium hydride; cold hydrogen pressure : 50 kgf/cm²]

Temperature, °C	Co : Al atomic ratio	Time, min	Saturates, % v/v
153	1 : 4	190	63
168	1 : 4	110	96
185	1 : 4	95	99
202	1 : 4	35	98

(ii) Effect of Concentration :

In the case of the catalyst system (a) containing the dehydrated metal chelate, a low concentration of 0.0005 mole of the chelate per 40 ml of benzene did not effect the reaction. However, the doubling of this concentration could lead to almost complete conversion. An amount of one millimole of the

Fig. 1. Absorption of hydrogen at various temperatures Catalyst : Cobalt(II) disalicylaldehyde-lithium aluminium hydride ; Substrate : 40 ml benzene

chelate was found to effect the facile conversion of benzene into cyclohexane catalyzed by all the three systems. Table 2 shows the effect of chelate concentration on the rate of hydrogenation of benzene into cyclohexane with the catalyst system (c).

TABLE 2—HYDROGENATION OF BENZENE AT DIFFERENT CATALYST CONCENTRATIONS

[Effect of chelate concentration on the rate of hydrogenation ; catalyst : cobalt(II) disalicylaldehyde-lithium aluminium hydride ; substrate : benzene 40 ml, temperature : 202°C and cold hydrogen pressure : 50 kgf/cm²]

Concentration of Co(Sal) ₂ , m mole/40 ml of benzene	Co : Al Atomic ratio	Time, min	Saturates, % v/v
1.000	1 : 4	35	98
0.666	1 : 4	65	100
0.500	1 : 4	120	97
0.333	1 : 4	140	95

(iii) Effect of Transition Metal to Aluminium ratio :

This is shown in Table 3 where the catalyst system is bisacetylaceton-ethylenediiminonickel(II)

TABLE 3—THE EFFECT OF Ni : Al ATOMIC RATIO

[Catalyst : bisacetylaceton-ethylenediiminonickel(II) dihydrate-lithium aluminium hydride ; substrate : 40 ml benzene, temperature : 235°C and cold hydrogen pressure : 50 kgf/cm²]

Ni : Al atomic ratio	Pressure at 200°C, kgf/cm ²	Time, min	Saturates, % v/v
1 : 1	80	60	42
1 : 2	80	25	96
1 : 3	75-80	25	98
1 : 4	75	20	99.5
1 : 5	70-75	20	99.5-100
1 : 6	75	25	99
1 : 7	75	30	98.5
1 : 8	80	35	99

-dihydrate-lithium aluminium hydride. The extent of hydrogenation sharply rose when the nickel : aluminium ratio was lowered from 1 : 1 to 1 : 2. Considering both the time and conversion, the optimum ratio appeared to be 1 : 4.

(iv) *Effect of Pressure*

A cold hydrogen pressure of one atmosphere at a temperature of 230° converted more than ninety per cent of benzene into cyclohexane with the system (a) as the catalyst, whereas at a pressure above 60 kgf/cm² but a temperature below 200° the reaction was very slow. The role of pressure was subservient to that of temperature.

Apart from the parameters discussed above, there were other factors such as the method of preparation of the complex, the water of crystallisation, the presence of impurity, the activity of lithium aluminium hydride, etc., which effected the rate and the yield of the reaction. Out of the three catalyst systems reported above, the first one was based on both hydrated and dehydrated chelates. It was interesting to note that the hydrated system was more active than the dehydrated. Perhaps under the conditions of the reaction the water molecules bound to the metal atom at the outer co-ordination sphere were expelled, thus producing nascent and vacant sites for benzene to occupy or the hydride bridge to form.

Mechanism of the Reaction :

Lithium aluminium hydride is used to prepare transition metal hydride complexes. The latter have been suggested as the catalytically active species in almost all the hydrogenation catalysts from the transition metal complexes¹⁰⁻¹³.

It is believed that a transition metal hydride species is formed by the reduction of the complex with lithium aluminium hydride as the reaction intermediate in the hydrogenation of benzene into cyclohexane⁵.

Benzene is co-ordinated to this intermediate before hydrogenation proceeds. It is difficult to say whether a step-wise or a concerted single step

hydrogenation process takes place. A step-wise process has been proposed by Lipovich, Shmidt and Kalechits¹⁴ for Ziegler-Natta catalysts. The rings in the metal chelates are perhaps fixed on the same plane by the central metal atom without steric hindrance. The X-ray studies of Ueno and Martell¹⁵ support the stability of such a co-planar structure, which may account for the formation of the proposed hydride bridge intermediate.

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